

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.14 Systematic literature review using a keyword-based search focused on visions of transformative change related to biodiversity and nature, nature's contributions to people (NCP) and good quality of life

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Description: The review corresponds to the Chapter 2 “Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people” of the IPBES transformative change assessment. The scoping document (IPBES-8/1 Annex II) outlines that Chapter 2 will examine the challenges of transformative change for nature and people, which involves integrating science-based and Indigenous and local knowledge-based understandings of biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people, considering normative ethics, diverse worldviews, and collective values for a sustainable future. The assessment will explore various attainable values, visions, and scenarios for a sustainable world, examining their connections to existing scenarios.

In this context, a systematic literature review was conducted using complementary approaches to search for visions, namely: 1) a systematic keyword-based search of peer-reviewed literature, 2) targeted searches across multiple subtopics, 3) a brainstorming and snowball-sampling approach for filling gaps identified in the keyword searches and 4) the incorporation of review results from the previous IPBES assessments.

Process overview

Protocol

Step 1: Peer-Reviewed Literature: Systematic keyword-based search of visions of nature

Description: The keyword chain was iteratively tested before its final use in identifying papers for review. Acknowledging that any effort to comprehensively define a keyword chain is limited, the key word chain used incorporates most of the terms commonly used in the literature focusing on nature, NCP and good quality of life. This review aims to contribute useful information for answering the mandate for Chapter 2 that refers to the types of visions of transformative change related to biodiversity and nature and its benefits to people that have not been explicitly addressed or have not been explicitly incorporated into decision-making.

Search languages: English

Search Engine: Clarivate Analytics Web of Science

Exact Search Date: 27 July 2022

Sample extracted: 392 papers

Location of the Data: 3-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_peer_reviewed_literature_raw(A)

Search terms for visions:

(vision* AND (future OR scenario OR pathway OR foresight OR narrative OR story* OR strategy OR projection OR simulation OR foresight OR outlook OR anticipat* OR regenerat* OR imagin* OR envision*)) AND (nature AND (environment* OR ecosystem OR biodiversity OR ecological OR cosmos OR creation OR "global commons" OR "mother earth" OR "mother nature")) AND (transform* OR ((system* OR radical OR transformative) AND change))

Filters and screening criteria applied: Titles and abstracts of the papers were screened to remove misfits, such as, items that do not address visions of nature, nature's contributions to people and good quality of life or make no reference to transformation.

Sample size: 88 papers

Location of the Data: 4-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_peer reviewed literature_cleaned(B).csv

Step 2: Snowball search for gap filling of peer-reviewed literature

Description: A snowball search was conducted with the aim of filling the gaps left by the systematic search. This approach focussed on the review of peer-reviewed visions in selected studies not identified and highlighted in the keyword searches. The materials were selected based on the expertise of the lead authors and based on the first order draft of the assessment reviewers' comments. Fifteen new papers were added to the previous 88 papers selected.

Search languages: English

Sample size: 15 papers

Location of the Data: 5-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_snowball(C)

Step 3: Coding of the visions

Filters and screening criteria applied: Papers from the searches described above were assessed using codes contained in (D) Row 57 “Positive Vision”, gaining a set of 76 coded positive visions of transformative change related to biodiversity and nature contributions to people (NCP) and good quality of life. These 76 coded positive visions were then coded according to F and included in the database of visions.

Sample size: 107 papers

Sample extracted: 76 coded positive transformative visions

Fields extracted: Rows 57 and 121

Location of the Data:

6-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_coding_criteria(D)

7-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_analysis(E)

Definition of files

	name	content	type
1	1-IPBES_TCA_chapter 2 DMR 2.14_peer_reviewed_literature_V2	Text	.pdf
2	2-IPBES_TCA_chapter 2 DMR 2.14_PRL_figure process_V2	Flow chart of the process	.jpg
3	3-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_raw(A)	392 papers	.csv
4	4-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_cleaned(B)	88 papers	.csv
5	5-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_snowball(C)	15 papers	.csv
6	6-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_coding_criteria(D)	Criteria	.csv
7	7-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.14_PRL_analysis(E)	76 visions	.csv